

Synthesis and structural characterization of a solvated dimorph of a hydrazonato-oxovanadium(V) complex with [OV(μ -O)VO] core

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Abstract : In this paper we report the synthesis and structural characterization of a different monoclinic variety of the title complex [V₂O₃(L)₂], incorporating the doubly deprotonated benzoyl hydrazone of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (H₂L) with *P2₁/c* space group that showed some differences in bonding patterns in the solid state with respect to its another monoclinic variety with *C2/c* space group reported earlier.

Keywords : Oxovanadium(V) complex, hydrazone complex, crystal structure, dimorphism.

Introduction

Polymorphism is the ability of a substance to adopt different internal structures and external forms, in response to different conditions of temperature and/or pressure and/or crystallization¹. So, different polymorphs have the same chemical and molecular compositions, differing only in the way those molecules are packed in the lattice. However, if any molecule crystallizes with or without solvent molecule(s) without changing their chemical identity then these different varieties may be termed as solvated dimorph as described by Seddon¹ (Desiraju² prefers to designate such type of crystalline varieties as pseudo-polymorphs). As a part of our program on the synthesis and characterization of new oxovanadium(IV/V) complexes with a family of benzoyl hydrazones of 2-hydroxy-acetophenone and its 5-substituted derivatives³⁻⁹, we have reported the dimorph of a V₂O₃⁴⁺-hydrazone complex containing the benzoyl hydrazone of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone^{4,5}, which probably the first report of dimorphism in this area. In this paper, we report the synthesis and structural characterization of a different crystalline variety of another [V₂O₃(L)₂] complex [where L²⁻ represents the doubly deprotonated benzoyl hydrazone of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (H₂L, I)], which shows

some differences in bonding patterns in the solid state with the other variety of this complex⁴, reported very recently from this laboratory.

Results and discussion

The monoclinic crystals of the complex [V₂O₃(L)₂] (with *P2₁/c* space group) containing benzene as solvent of crystallization were obtained from the aerial oxidation of [V^{IV}O(L)(bipy)] associated with the elimination of bipy from the coordination sphere of vanadium. This reaction can be represented as :

Molecular view of the complex is given in Fig. 1 and the selected bond parameters are collected in Table 1. In this monoclinic variety of the complex, two structurally very similar but crystallographically distinct molecules are present in the crystal lattice and the bridging oxygen atoms have no crystallographic symmetry (*cf.* in its other monoclinic variety, the bridging oxygens are lying on a crystallographic 2-fold axis such that two halves of each of the two molecules are crystallographically equivalent⁴). The two halves of each of the two molecules, however,

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of $[V_2O_3(L)_2]$ complex showing the atom numbering scheme with ellipsoid at 50% probability.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) of the complex

Bond distances

V(1)-O(1)	1.576(3)	V(2)-O(5)	1.570(3)
V(1)-O(2)	1.814(2)	V(2)-O(6)	1.815(3)
V(1)-O(3)	1.951(2)	V(2)-O(7)	1.932(2)
V(1)-O(4)	1.807(2)	V(2)-O(4)	1.797(2)
V(1)-N(1)	2.101(3)	V(2)-N(3)	2.109(3)
V(1)-V(2)	3.0018(9)	V(4)-O(12)	1.578(3)
V(3)-O(8)	1.576(3)	V(4)-O(13)	1.818(2)
V(3)-O(9)	1.797(2)	V(4)-O(14)	1.934(2)
V(3)-O(10)	1.944(2)	V(4)-O(11)	1.793(2)
V(3)-O(11)	1.818(2)	V(4)-N(7)	2.104(3)
V(3)-N(5)	2.103(3)		

V(3)-V(4)	2.9976(8)		
Bond angles :			
O(1)-V(1)-O(2)	103.52(13)	O(5)-V(2)-O(6)	103.73(15)
O(1)-V(1)-O(3)	102.07(12)	O(5)-V(2)-O(7)	102.78(14)
O(1)-V(1)-O(4)	107.65(6)	O(5)-V(2)-O(4)	107.64(14)
O(1)-V(1)-N(1)	101.15(13)	O(5)-V(2)-N(3)	101.51(15)
O(2)-V(1)-O(3)	148.81(11)	O(6)-V(2)-O(7)	148.16(12)
O(2)-V(1)-O(4)	103.23(11)	O(6)-V(2)-O(4)	102.52(11)
O(2)-V(1)-N(1)	82.75(11)	O(6)-V(2)-N(3)	82.79(11)
O(3)-V(1)-O(4)	85.55(10)	O(7)-V(2)-O(4)	85.82(10)
O(3)-V(1)-N(1)	75.03(10)	O(7)-V(2)-N(3)	74.88(11)
O(3)-V(1)-V(2)	61.38(7)	O(7)-V(2)-V(1)	61.30(8)
O(4)-V(1)-N(1)	148.05(11)	O(12)-V(4)-O(13)	103.94(14)
V(1)-O(4)-V(2)	112.77(12)	O(12)-V(4)-O(14)	103.42(13)
O(8)-V(3)-O(9)	103.41(13)	O(12)-V(4)-O(11)	109.14(13)
O(8)-V(3)-O(10)	101.58(12)	O(12)-V(4)-N(7)	101.04(13)
O(8)-V(3)-O(11)	106.83(6)	O(13)-V(4)-O(14)	147.37(12)
O(8)-V(3)-N(5)	101.22(12)	O(13)-V(4)-O(11)	102.14(11)
O(9)-V(3)-O(10)	149.52(11)	O(13)-V(4)-N(7)	82.87(11)
O(9)-V(3)-O(11)	102.80(11)	O(13)-V(4)-V(3)	111.03(9)
O(9)-V(3)-N(5)	83.21(10)	O(14)-V(4)-O(11)	85.24(10)
O(9)-V(3)-V(4)	110.08(8)	O(14)-V(4)-N(7)	74.73(10)
O(10)-V(3)-O(11)	86.23(10)	O(11)-V(4)-N(7)	146.93(11)
O(10)-V(3)-N(5)	75.03(10)		
O(11)-V(3)-N(5)	148.87(11)		
V(3)-O(11)-V(4)	112.23(12)		

have closely matching dimensions. The coordination sphere of the metal is of the VO_4N type and the geometry at the metal center can best be fitted to a distorted square pyramid with oxo-O(1/5/8/12) at the apex. The phenolate-O(2/6/9/13), the enolate-O(3/7/10/14), the imine-N(1/3/5/7) atoms of the fully deprotonated H_2L ligand in its enol form and the bridging oxygen O(4/11) atom constitute the tetragonal plane from which the V(1), V(2), V(3) and V(4) are displaced respectively by 0.525 Å, 0.531 Å, 0.512 Å and 0.544 Å from the mean plane towards the terminal O(1), O(5), O(8) and O(12) atoms respectively. The average O(axial)-V-O/N(equatorial) angle is $\sim 104^\circ$, which is only slightly different from the average angle of 102° for a square pyramidal complex (C_{4v}) as explained by Muetterties and Guggenberger¹⁰. The extent of distortion from the perfect square-pyramidal geometry can also be quantified by the τ parameter¹¹ (equal to $\Delta/60^\circ$, dif-

ference between the largest and next-to-largest ligand-metal-ligand angles). $\Delta = 0$, $\tau = 0$, for idealized square pyramid and $\tau = 1$, for trigonal bipyramid. The τ values are 0.01, 0.003, 0.01 and 0.007 respectively for V(1), V(2), V(3) and V(4) centers, indicating very slight distortion from the perfect square pyramidal structure.

The dihedral angles between the bases V(1) and V(2) is 58.95° and that for V(3) and V(4) bases is 58.42° . Two terminal oxo-O atoms in each of the two molecules are mutually *trans* lying on opposite sides of the V-O-V plane. The distance of the O(1) and O(5) atoms from the V(1)-O(4)-V(2) plane is respectively 0.916 Å and 0.904 Å [while that of the O(8) and O(12) atoms from the V(3)-O(11)-V(4) plane is 0.878 Å and 0.944 Å respectively]. The O(1)-V(1)-V(2)-O(5) torsion angle is 102.66° and that of O(8)-V(3)-V(4)-O(12) is 103.69° . The V-O^t ($t =$

terminal) [1.570(3)–1.578(3) Å], the V-O^b (b = bridging) [1.793(2)–1.818(2) Å] distances and the other bond lengths and bond angles are very similar to the reported analogous hydrazone complexes^{4,5,12,13}. The O-C, N-C and N-N distances are consistent with the enolate form of the corresponding ligand^{3-8,12,13}. An examination of the bond length parameters reveals a general order : V-O^t < V-O^b ~ V-O^p (p = phenolic) < V-O^e (e = enolic), which can be explained on the basis of basicity of donor atoms and their π -bonding ability. V(1)-O(4)-V(2) and V(3)-O(11)-V(4) angles are 112.77(12)° and 112.23(12)° respectively, which are also consistent with the reported values of analogous hydrazone complexes^{4,5,12,13}. The non-bonded V(1)-V(2) and V(3)-V(4) distances are respectively 3.0018(9) Å and 2.9976(8) Å, which are also very similar to those of other reported hydrazone complexes^{4,5,12,13}.

The main differences between the present crystalline variety and the previously reported other variety of this complex are : (i) it belongs to the $P2_1/c$ space group compared to the $C2/c$ space group observed in its other variety⁴ and (ii) in the structure (Fig. 1) of this variety, the bridging oxygen atoms of the two molecules do not lie on a crystallographic 2-fold axis and as a result of that the two halves of each of the two molecules are crystallographically non-equivalent.

Conclusion :

This crystalline variety represents the first solvated dimorph of [V₂O₃(L)₂] complex in which the bridging oxygen atoms do not lie on a crystallographic 2-fold axis.

Experimental

Materials :

5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone was procured from Aldrich. Benzoyl hydrazine was purchased from E. Merck. Acetylacetone, vanadyl sulphate pentahydrate and 2,2'-bipyridine were obtained from Loba Chemical Company (India). [V^{IV}O(L)(bipy)]⁹ was synthesized by the reported method. All other reagents were of A.R. grade, obtained from commercial sources and used without further purification.

Preparation of the metal complexes :

The complex was synthesized in the following way : The orange-red [V^{IV}O(L)(bipy)] (0.05 g, 0.1 mmol) was dissolved in 15 cm³ CH₂Cl₂ followed by the addition of

equal volume of benzene and kept for slow evaporation at room temperature. After several days black crystals (suitable for X-ray work) were obtained in 85% yield (Found : C, 55.46; H, 3.83; N, 6.63. Calcd. for C₇₈H₆₂Cl₄N₈O₁₄V₄ (1680.92) : C, 55.68; H, 3.69; N, 6.66%).

X-Ray data collection and refinement :

For X-ray structure determination, data were measured with Mo K α radiation at 150 K using a Bruker SMART APEX three circle diffractometer equipped with a CCD area detector. Data analyses were carried out with the CrysAlis program¹⁴ and the structure was solved using direct methods with the SHELXS-97 program¹⁵. Absorption corrections were carried out with the ABSPACK program¹⁶ and the non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The hydrogen atoms bonded to carbon were included in geometric positions and given thermal parameters equivalent to 1.2 times those of the atom to which they were attached. The structures were refined on F^2 using SHELXL-97 program¹⁵ and the molecular graphics were computed using PLATON¹⁷. All crystallographic data are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Crystal data and structure determination summary of the complex

Empirical formula	C ₆₀ H ₄₄ Cl ₄ N ₈ O ₁₄ V ₄ ·3C ₆ H ₆
Formula weight	1680.92
Crystal colour	Black
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$
<i>a</i> (Å)	22.0453(14)
<i>b</i> (Å)	15.1806(9)
<i>c</i> (Å)	22.8521(14)
α (°)	90
β (°)	96.339(1)
γ (°)	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	7600.9(8)
<i>Z</i>	4
ρ_{calc} (g cm ⁻³)	1.469
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.687
<i>F</i> (000)	3432
Data/restraints/parameters	13380/0/977
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.912
<i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i> ₀)] <i>R</i> 1, <i>wR</i> 2	0.0539, 0.1235
<i>R</i> indices (all data) <i>R</i> 1, <i>wR</i> 2	0.0870, 0.1452

Supplementary material :

CCDC 714726 contains the supplementary crystallographic data which can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 IEZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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